

ISic0311

I.Sicily inscription 0311

Language

Latin

Type

funerary; honorific

Material

volcanic

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2014

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Universita degli studi di Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. M(arcus) Petronius Rufinus VI(se)vir Aug(ustalis)

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Marcus Petronius Rufinus, sevir Augustalis

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491518

EDR 141130

EDCS 21900346

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae*

Borussicae editum. Berlin. At 10.7027 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/books/CILv10pII1883>)

Manganaro, G. 1988. La Sicilia da Sesto Pompeo a Diocleziano. *ANRW*. 2.11.1: 3-89. At 47, tav.17.26

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